

**Exile as Self-Inscription in Micere Mugo's
*My Mother's Poem and Other Songs***

Senayon Olaoluwa

University of Ibadan

Abstract

This essay reads Micere Mugo's collection *My Mother's Poem and Other Songs* (1994) as an illustration of self-inscription in exile. It argues that beyond the sundry concerns articulated in the collection, an understanding of her work must begin with an acknowledgment of her place among second generation Anglophone African poets. By paying particular attention to the work's investment in orature and performance, the paper contests the reductionist critique that ascribes little poetic significance to the collection. The essay concludes that her reflection on exile destabilizes the hegemonic construction of home as a stable category, but nevertheless projects hope for Africa as homeland.

Keywords: Micere Mugo, Exile, Self-inscription, Kenya, *My Mother's Poem and Other Songs*

Résumé

Le présent article sur la poésie de Micere Mugo intitulé *My Mother's Poem and other Songs* (1994), sert d'illustration de l'auto-inscription en exil. L'auteur soutient le fait qu'au-delà des diverses préoccupations articulées dans la collection, une compréhension de son travail doit commencer par une reconnaissance de la place de l'auteur parmi les poètes africaines anglophones de la deuxième génération. En accordant une attention particulière à l'investissement de l'œuvre dans l'oralité et dans la performance, l'article est contre la critique réductionniste qui attribue peu de signification poétique à la collection. En conclusion, on constate que sa réflexion sur l'exil, déstabilise la construction hégémonique du foyer comme catégorie stable, bien qu'elle donne de l'espoir à l'Afrique comme notre patrie.

Mots-clés: Micere Mugo, Exil, Auto-inscription, Kenya, *Poème de ma mère et autres chansons*

Introduction

The experience of exile is an enduring focus in African poetry. Poets in East Africa have always demonstrated an awareness of their responsibility in a manner that ensures they do not sacrifice sensitivity to social dynamics for artistic mysticism. According to Yesufu (328), poetry in the region "is clearly focused on a living social reality, presenting various facets of this reality, especially the social lapses and the results of these defects on the overall social order". Against this backdrop, I read exile as a consequence of the social realities that designate "social lapses" in the region and which is succinctly captured in Micere Mugo's poetry. The discussion hopes to additionally underscore the assumption that

literary responses to the alienating conditions of homeland often find balance in the simultaneous critique of destinations of exilic living (Thorpe 1).

Mugo is one of Kenya's notable writers and literary scholars living in exile. Her collection of poems *My Mother's Poem and Other Songs* is her second volume and can be described as thoroughly steeped in reflections on exile, though with nuanced cadences that for the most part appear as articulations in activism. This in itself is not surprising, considering that her exile, which began in 1982 after a failed military coup, was predicated on a life of activism and constant interrogation of establishment, like her male compatriot, fellow exile and writer Ngugi wa Thiong'o. As if conscious of her ever critical stance and the need to put up a defence in which even the establishment can also ironically be held responsible, she recently made the following remarks at a 2012 public lecture at the University of Nairobi where she had previously taught between 1978 and 1982 before being forced into exile: "This university taught me to continue my rebellion. This university taught me to continue questioning. This university taught me to be fearless irrespective of what is happening around me" (1). Putting her in the same mould as Ngugi then is all the more justifiable as they both can also be described as "soul-mates". During their career at the University of Nairobi, they together created in the masses of Kenyans an awareness of oppression in the lingo and performance of power by the political class.

Any surprise then that after the 1982 failed coup, Mugo became a victim of state harassment until the option of exile was forced upon not only her, but also on her two young daughters. Her kind of exile in those early years of the 1980s also had a dimension of extremism to it because she was literally stripped of her Kenyan citizenship. In response, it took the intervention of the government of Zimbabwe to grant her citizenship, otherwise she would have remained for some years without a country of origin. To that extent, Marsh-Lockett and West i) undermine the capability of contemporary political intolerance when they consider as "dated" the idea of banishment of citizens by governments, limiting the practice to "ancient civilisations". For, as the case of Mugo has shown, her banishment carried the forbidding extremism of finality and signalled in the material moment the termination of a link between Kenya as place of birth and origin. Knowing that the collection was for the most part thought out in exile, with some of the poems having been realised on stage, a fact to which she testifies in the preface to the collection, it is logical to assert that the entire collection is a reflection on exile.

Within the mapping of the second generation poets that have reflected on the experience of exile, Mugo is very important and holds for us in this discussion the image of double value. Such poets include Niyi Osundare, Jack Mapanje, Mongane Wally Serote, Kofi Anyidoho, Ochia Ofeimun, Syl Cheney Coker, Jared Angira, among others. Their poetry designates what Funsho Aiyejina (122) has famously termed the "alter-native tradition". Though the caption immediately speaks to a certain category of Nigerian poets, their contemporaries in other countries fit into the mould. They are so designated for the radical departure of their poetry from what obtains in the poetry of older poets like Okigbo, Brutus, Soyinka, among others. Therefore, the ascription of double value to her person stems from knowing that not only is she in exile, her poetry also provides a fresh dimension to the various ways in which

the “libratory” essence of exilic experience can find expression in a poet's work beyond the otherwise obvious significations. Her approach in the collection provides nuances that reflect on exile without directly announcing it. The approach is also significant because the reflections speak to the notion of mobility which allows for a traversing of spaces through which the plights of millions as women, children, blacks and oppressed people of all races are brought into focus.

In his review of *My Mother's Poem and Other Songs* and Mugo's collection of critical essays, *African Orature and Human Rights* Adeeko (222), affirms a synergy between the two by declaring that while the critical essays make up her "theory" book, the collection of poems constitutes her "practice" book. By also observing that the theory book preceded the practice book, it stands to reason that Mugo taps into the human rights heritage and legacy of African folklore and orature to seek validation and endorsement for her embodied life of activism.

It is additionally crucial to consider the oral context of the Ndia orature that serves as the theoretical frame for Mugo's "practice" book. The context evoked is that of the ordinary everyday demotic art and practice in which both the oral artist and the audience are co-located. Reinforcing this trope with respect to Mugo's artistic oeuvre in *My Mother's Poem and Others Songs* is necessary because of the tendency to dismiss the work as making so many claims to orality when in actual fact it has little to show for it (Ojaide 631). For that matter, the collection is read as pinpointing communal popular performance in the context of orature. It explains why performance cannot be disarticulated from audience because the audience can only join the oral artist in the call-and-response obligation only if the oral artist does not mystify the audience

But more importantly, the import of the co-location of artist and audience is reinforced in the collection by the very sense in which call-and-response is privileged. It is a trope that runs throughout the text by the use of refrain in almost every poem. This aesthetic approach reinforces the sense of urgency and desperation with which poets of the second generation intend to create and maintain a strong link between their art and the people. Their poetry is concerned not only about postcolonial Africa's "desperate condition" (Osundare 27); it also bears a sort of radical simplicity that is complemented by performance (Olaoluwa 461). Moreover, the seeming simplicity of her art should not be confused with poor art because where songs are to be rendered for communal participation, simplicity becomes a vital ingredient through which the relevance of art is reinforced. As has been asserted earlier, an informed understanding of Mugo's art with respect to her theory and practice must begin with situating it within the broad-based context of exile which has provided the fulcrum for her intervention.

Art as Protest and Displacement

What then are the concerns of Mugo's art? According to Adeeko (224), the collection can be divided into four distinct concerns: "children and youth, feminism and womanism, common

political good and moving personal reflections". While this may serve in a sense to suggest how the work may be read, I propose in this essay a more productive approach to the concerns that are given articulation in the collection. This must begin by foregrounding Mugo's exilic condition: how the condition cannot be divested of the issues with which her poetry is concerned. For that matter, there is all through an abiding commitment to a form of social critique which does not only stay true to the Ndia template of oral performance, but is additionally transcendental of this template in the very sense it stages an interrogation of all forms of arbitrary performance of power. By painting every scenario as uncomplimentary and identifying victims and perpetrators, her poetry raises hope of the ultimate triumph of the victims. Such representation speaks to the hope about the termination of exile, when the hope of a better home and return is created for the exile in the end. The opening poem lives up to this billing when it engages the tenderness of birth and childhood as both metaphor and imagery that are capable of wrestling with all forms of oppressive symbols and triumphing over them in the end. It is also instructive to note that a preceding note on the poem acknowledges how the poem was inspired by exile, having been written for her daughters "during our mountainous life in exile" (1). But in paying tribute to her daughters, the poem is invested with agency to explore childhood beyond the realm of innocence and vulnerability. Referring to them as "The beautiful ones" [who] were born"[1-3), not only is there an attempt to contest Ayi Kwei Armah's negative verdict on postcolonial Africa, their birth also becomes an experience through which Kenya's colonial and postcolonial history of violence is evoked in order to reinforce an envisaged transformative agency of birth.

The informed perspective of the persona in the poem consists in the nuanced evocation of history as that which commences with an acknowledgment of a pre-colonial era reputable for affirming the harmony of society and nature. But while this is so, the overwhelming condition of tyranny turns nature in the poem into the imagery of violence as we witness the birth of "The Beautiful Ones"/ under leopard skies/under roaring thunder/under flooding rain [and]/under drowning earth" (1). The activities of the natural elements are not inherently violent, but we are compelled to read violence in them when they are characterized by extremism. For, while the metaphor of "leopard skies" is suggestive of extreme sunshine and drought, the extremism of rainfall causes flood and leads to environmental compromise which is manifest in the "drowning" of the "earth". As seen above, replenishment is tied to rainfall, but its extremity would wreck havoc and become counter-productive. The elements of nature are moreover analogous to the performance of power that is required for the well being of society. However, when put into extreme use, power becomes an instrument of violence through which the people are compromised. It then explains why beyond the allegory of natural violence, human violence is explored in the poem through an invocation of colonial violence, which nevertheless met fierce opposition in the colonised. It is equally instructive to know that in accounting for the agency of leadership in opposition to colonial violence, Mugo maintains an uncommon rendition of gender balance. That is, unlike most historical accounts of nationalist struggles which tend to assign backseat significance to women, Mugo demonstrates how gender balance in resistance to leadership is central to the history of liberation struggle in Kenya. We not only read of "Koitalel arap Kirima" and "Kimathi wa Wachiuri" notable Kenyan male freedom fighters, we also read about "Me Katilili" and "Muthoni wa Kirima", women

who mobilised their people to put up strong resistance to colonial rule and violence. Specifically, Mekatilili Wa Menza is remembered for mobilising her people in Giriama, a coastal area against British colonial administration and its notoriety for land dispossession in Kenya. Similarly, Muthoni wa Kirima is acknowledged as the only female field marshal of the MauMau rebellion which played a critical role in the dismantling of British colonialism in Kenya. The recollection then goes to give validation to Ojwang's (106) assertion that: "Women's agency... exceed[s] the strictures of patriarchal culture, for the historicity of their participation cannot be completely written out by a stilted historiography. [The] absence or silences of historiographical practice in regard to women does not change the intrinsic historical importance of their immersion in society".

The violence of colonialism, further extended as the birth of "the beautiful ones", also invokes the memory of "the spoils" of both colonists and European writers who dispossessed colonised Kenyans by grabbing their lands in the process of which original land owners were turned into squatters or literally dispossessed (See Ngugi wa Thiong'o, *Dreams in a Time of War*). Referring to writers such as "Karen Blixen", "De la Mere" and "Elspeth Huxley" is thus a decisive allusion through which light is shed on how certain western literary writers benefitted directly from colonial capitalism in Africa. The evocation is reminiscent of the investment of western writers and inventors like Alexander Pope and Isaac Newton in the Atlantic Slave Trade (Kerr-Ritchie 354). In this case, the invocation of the Kenyan resistance icons reminds us of the colonial violence as brute force. There is also a strong sense in which the allusion to European writers with settler history in Kenya shows the other side of colonial violence as one which instrumentalised literature. It invariably shows the very sense in which colonial violence is both frontal and subtle. As Matthew Carotenuto and Brett Shadle (2) have argued, we cannot fully come to terms with postcolonial violence in Kenya without acknowledging their origin in "the racially charged settler society and colonial courts". In spite of all this, and amidst "neo-colonial treachery" and "under person-eat-person/development economics", we are consistently reminded through the repetitive trope of the refrain that "The beautiful ones/were born", leaving us with much hope of a bright future:

in the lowlands of despair
through valleys of elusive hope
across ridges of obstinate resistance
on the highlands of mounting optimism
by the flowing rivers of momentous triumph
aboard growing visions of internationalist victory (3)

Generally, the adamant hope that radiates in the concluding lines set the tone for the section concerned with childhood and youth. It takes readers beyond postcolonial Kenya to engage with African and other social imaginaries. This is the case with "In Praise of Afrika's Children" where in spite of the overwhelming condition of lack and deprivation "from Harlem to Soweto" (7), the children are said to be "reborn". As Obeyesekere has argued,

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transformation is common to narratives of rebirth across the world (cited in Coward 567). The significance this holds as a motif in Mugo's poetry lies in its capacity to mediate transformation against all odds. There is for that matter an advocacy for transcending the obvious limiting conditions that prevent the realisation of dreams of greatness in youth. This is why in singing "a love song" there is an ultimate goal which is transcendental of the values often associated with lullabies:

reborn
 through thunder
reborn
 through pain
reborn
 through death
reborn
 through vision
reborn
 through love (11)

Therefore, the agency of motivation is clear in this poem by the very sense in which it canvasses self-awareness to mediate a desirable change from the present state of atrophy. This clearly speaks to what Hoban Jr. (276) has termed the "rhetorical rituals of rebirth", which among other things presupposes "a heightened awareness of self and others expressed in multivocal symbols". But more instructive is his assertion that "defining rhetorical rituals entails a regard for contradictions, perhaps never to be resolved, in the nature of these acts" (275). For, ordinarily, notions of "thunder", "death", "pain" are in contradistinction to those of "vision" and "love"; but as asserted in this poem, all these must merge to evolve a transformative atmosphere in which youthful potentials are realised in concrete developmental terms. Yet, this is not a call that is limited by space because it is simultaneously global in the very sense in which it makes an appeal to children and youth not only from "Cape to Cairo" (10), but also "from New York to San Francisco/From Trinidad to Belize/ from Nova Scotia to Vancouver/from Brazil to Grenada" (11). The import of hope for development, especially when we take the repetition of "reborn" as instructive in the concluding part of this poem, compels us to invoke the memory of the Enlightenment. As Eliuz (329) recalls, the Enlightenment galvanised the western world into an unprecedented epoch of development through an observance of a transformative ritual process of self-awareness. The bottom-line in the poem is thus that Africa's children too require learning from this. It is through being able to free themselves from the forces of limitation that their dreams can be realised. The admonition finds its finest articulation in "The Isle of Youth" which is consciously described as tapping into orature to fight oppression:

It is an evening of
naming oppression
through poetry

in the orature tradition. (18)

In poems like "Mother Afrika's Matriots" and "To be a Feminist Is" Mugo validates the assertion that the prevailing circumstances in which postcolonial women are caught with respect to their subjectivities informs their agency in constructing and organising "resistance both within and beyond the nation" (Talbayev 114). The level of resistance that we encounter in the poems is connected to Mugo's life as that which is committed to the articulation of women's subjectivities not only during her period of "settledness" at home, but also during the period of her exile. Again, the level of resistance is connected to the doubly problematic nature of black womanhood. According to Sokhan Benga:

We are in a world of contradictions; a world where, all the time, I have to justify—to the others— why I am a dark black woman writer of Africa. Because it's a challenge to be first black, second a woman, and third a female writer, and in the end an African, a part of the old Africa—the forgotten continent without culture, without thought, which only knows dance and songs, diseases (AIDS in particular), misery, wars, genocide—the forgotten one because this suits some people. It's the same image Europe gave to Africa four centuries ago to explain and justify slavery and colonialism and other forms of domination Mama Africa has known and continues to know today. (8)

It then requires that an unmistakable eloquence is given to women's subjectivities beyond the shores of an original homeland and in a sense that reinforces transnational gender solidarity. The note to "Mother Afrika's Matriots" for instance reveals that it is "A contribution towards the urgent task of engendering Pan-Africanism". Not surprisingly, the poem proceeds to recount "our womanful lives" and "our history" (29), an indication that African women's subjectivities and agencies can no longer be consigned to the background. With the refrain as "Mother Afrika's Matriots", the poem traverses vast lands from Africa to Europe and America, invoking and evoking the history of African women and those of African descent in diaspora who have contributed one way or the other in resistance to all forms of repression of black humanity in the world. Arranged to imitate the incantatory ritual of performance, the refrain works together with the long list of roll call of these "matriots". It asserts the place of the various women in the making of pan-Africanism, thereby investing the performance with the solemnity of important history.

In "To be a Feminist Is", the sense we make of the poem is enhanced, as usual, by the opening note to the poem, which is "an effort to liberate the concept of feminism from abduction by Western bourgeois appropriators" (36). What this implies is that feminism is constitutive of African epistemology and should be articulated with a peculiar African slant, rather than being overwritten by western paradigms. In Meko's (189) assertion, such consciousness has informed the conceptualisation of various slants of African feminism by women of Africa and those of African descent. They deplore the inherent derailment to certain African ideals when there is an imposition of certain western paradigms that do not

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chime with African cultural dynamics, to say nothing of the cosmological peculiarities. From the various slants of African feminism such as 'Third World Feminism', 'African Feminism', 'Womanism', 'Stiwanism' (ibid.), Mugo articulates a consciousness that is obviously in contradistinction to what is otherwise normative in western theoretical paradigms of feminism. The poem indeed demonstrates familiarity with basic assumptions of feminism in the West. It nevertheless foregrounds African feminism as one that takes into account some of the fundamentals of African humanism through which a sense of collectivism is invested in the making of the African world view. In the end:

For me
to be a feminist is

to be the mother
of my daughters
it is
to be the daughter
of my mother
it is
to be more than
a survivor
it is
to be a creator
it is
to be a woman. (42)

Banished and driven into exile from her country of birth with the extremism of state intolerance which stripped her of the citizenship of the country of her birth, Mugo appropriates the whole space of the African continent as her own. She does so in a manner that is reminiscent of Dennis Brutus' figure of the "troubadour" traversing all his land (See Senanu and Vincent 2003). Nation is therefore a recurring concern in her poetry of exile as she reflects on the various challenges of homeland with all the nuances of patriotism that also speak to the contradictions inherent in her poetry of exile. As is common to the poems in the collection, Mugo makes it clear from the outset in the preceding note to "We will Rise and Build the Nation" that it is meant to express a kind of contestation "*In defiance of neo-colonial dictators, reminding them that even the darkest of nights breaks into daylight and that their days are truly numbered*" (68). Such affirmation validates the assumption that the "blessings of exile" consist in how poetry freely "interrogates the notions of modernity and progress, victory and loss, and nationalism and patriotism" (Mir 311). Ordinarily, her expulsion from her homeland should have discouraged her from expressing such passionate concern for the fate of the continent which bore down heavily on the people. It was a condition that invested political independence with cosmetic values as collusion between African tyrants and western powers made the continent more vulnerable than it was in the days of colonialism. The poem captures this contradictory situation in the temporal juxtaposition that characterises it:

At independence

colonial collaborators snatched
our national liberation flag
highjacking our independence
with cunning serpentine imposture
twisting into a rope
with which they strangled our hopes
leaving us under neo-colonial barrenness.

Under neo-colonialism

our bodies are consumed
with keeping perpetual wakes
through nights of econo-political
funerals
Our nerves are wrenched
by persisting rending screams
from abused human rights victims (70-71)

Invariably, it is arguable that we can situate the above within the domain of what Hincapie (447) describes as the discourse of "expulsion, departure, exile and return" precisely. As she explains, there is a category of reflection which is best described as "a writing that is vulnerable—a self-ethnographical writing which takes us somewhere we couldn't otherwise go and moves us to identify intensely with those one is writing about." The texture and tone of "We will Rise and Build the Nation" shows clearly that in spite of her expulsion from home, Mugo still holds dearly to the ideals of nationalism. Hers is a determination to interrogate and fight the neo-colonial structures that rein in the aspiration towards greatness in a number of African countries. By extending the reflection beyond the temporal realm of the past, Mugo foregrounds the agency of contestation. She represents the agency as necessary for a transformation of the prevailing circumstances of both independence and neo-colonialism. This she does by instituting actions of contestation in the present while animating hopes about the future. Therefore: "But we refuse/to leave our anger/scattered/on the wasteland/of our enemy's plunder" (70). This gives hope to the restoration of national dignity through the imagery of exhumed "graveyards/ of our collective/conscience" (70). Doing this will ultimately result in "levelling the tombs/ of our destroyed nationhood" (70). By canvassing for actions in the transformation of such lousy conditions of homeland, nationhood becomes a burden on the mind of the exile. The agency of writing, especially women writing, in dealing with such condition cannot be undermined. As Watson (25) has argued, physical return is not necessarily a precondition for the mediation between national temporalities as writing "transforms... women into inadvertent mediators between the past and present, homeland and diaspora, oral history and writing." Nevertheless, Mugo's hope in the transformation of the dystopian conditions of homeland through nation building is inclusive of physical return at this stage of the envisaged social reforms in order that:

We will fly home

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exiled patriots
banished patriots
landing them home
on a newly built
Me Katilili Airport

We will plough

the barren fields
of our ravished
national economy
producing a surplus
of our full growth

We will rise

and build a nation
moulding from the pieces
of an oppressive history
an unassailable monument
grafted with justice for all
enshrined with limitless hope. (71-71)

It is this same enthusiasm about nation building and return that finds a robust exploration in the symbolism of "Plant a Tree". Beyond the cosmopolitan tincture of the planting ritual in far away Le Moyne College, USA with her fellow compatriot Wangari Muta Maathai (73) speaks to the act itself as grounded in African folk rituals. It also presupposes that contrary to western condescending assumptions about helping Africa to wake up from its eco-slumber (William Slaymaker 2001: 132), the continent through its rich cultural heritage has always been eco-critical all along. By dramatising the tree planting activism of Wangari Maathai as a cultural practice steeped in ritual and folklore, Mugo rejects the backwaters location western scholarship assigns Africa in the discourse of eco-criticism. This way, eco-criticism is dramatised as a long-established practice beyond the recent temporal mapping of the West.

"My Mother's Poem" or the Poetry of Exile

The eponymous poem, "My Mother's Poem", is composed "*in celebration of progressive African Orature, with all its sustaining wisdom of and aesthetic appeal*"(79). Presented as a telephone conversation between mother and daughter, the poem however does more than this. In it, a dialogue with one's mother over the loss of one's father animates discussions of home and exile. Apparently the call is put through by her mother to announce the death of her father. Having been banished from the homeland, the father's death becomes doubly painful and instigates a longing for homeland. The discussion is laced with an aura of loss and mourning over a loved one. It additionally turns out to be an inventive way of responding to a personal condition of exile and the appropriate response relative to her specific exilic condition. According to Githire (74), there are certain "processes and

mechanisms through which displaced women 'place' themselves at home, in exile and abroad". "My Mother's Poem" is thus an illustration of such processes and mechanisms. Specifically, Mugo's strategy here is to mobilise dramatic elements of dialogue, conflict and resolution to reinforce what should be the appropriate response to the tripartite notion of exile, home and return. This is so because exilic experiences are not equally so, as they differ from person to person and group to group. While the differentials in exilic experience implicate the location of home and the personality of exiles themselves, a number of other issues in the rendition of such discrimination are accounted for as well in the variables of race, class, religious and sectarian affiliations, and economic dynamics of the host nations. This explains why Tsaaio (98) argues that in contemporary times, there are "multiple and shifting networks of significations that undergird the very constitution and definition of home, exile and the exiled." A further explication of the ambivalence and multiple responses to the exilic condition also finds articulation in the postmodernity of our times. As Spunta (285) puts it, there continues to be a debate around the question of "place and landscape, positing them as memory, contemplation, and imagination, highlighting the affective and relational experience of place, and voicing the postmodern condition of inhabiting displacement." To that extent, Mugo's poetry speaks to the postmodernity of displacement in a way that contests a linear dimension to the unpacking of the associated notions of home, exile and return. She problematises them through the privileging of dramatic aesthetics in order to justify how exilic attitude is relational and makes sense in the contextualisation of individual exilic experiences.

"My Mother's Poem" thus opens the "heaviness and sorrow" that often weigh down the bereaved in the wake of the interment of a loved one. The heaviness of heart is made more poignant by the condition of banishment and exile which has prevented her from attending the funeral. The natural sense of longing that this condition creates becomes the source of the reflections and exchange between a home-based mother and an exiled daughter in a faraway land from the shores of the homeland. Quite expectedly,

The day after
 my father
 was buried
the distance
 between home
 and exile
suddenly doubled
and through windows
 of helplessness
I hurled out
 courage
turning it
 into a heap
 of despair (79)

The double sense of exile, to begin with, is logical because there is a conceptual link between death and exile. In such instances, death can be either literal or metaphorical or in some cases, it can designate a whole range of things in which both the literal and the metaphorical are implicated. Therefore the double sense of exile is implicated in her status as one that is banished from her homeland and cannot exercise the freedom to return and witness the funeral of her late father. At another level, according to Grebe (491), there is also a sense in which to be exiled is to be dead precisely because while the exiled individual is biologically alive, he/she is nonetheless culturally dead, having been cut off from intimate participation in certain practices. Against this backdrop, for a bereaved who cannot participate in the rites of passage for her late father, the double sense of exile also compels us to affirm the condition as capable of repeating doubling at the level of death. This implies that the non-participation in the rites of passages is itself an instantiation of death because the void created by the absence of the bereaved exile is as good as another instance of death. The feeling for those at home is thus that of double loss because the actual death and the loss it instigates are worsened by the absence of the exiled who cannot return home to pay their last respect to the dead. It then becomes understandable why the reality of one's exclusion from a cultural practice such as the rites of passage can create a sense of hopelessness that can shatter "courage/ turning it/ into a heap/ of despair".

But the lousy exilic condition and the impossibility of immediate return are subsequently made for in the telephone conversation. What begins as a narrative in soliloquy is animated by her mother's response to agony of tears which makes her "drowned/ the telephone line/ with rivers of tears" (79). The hyperbolic imagery of "rivers of tears" underscores the feeling of defeat by the state act of banishment. Her father's death pinpoints the seriousness of her banishment, seeing she cannot return to observe the important rites of passage. Basically the situation warrants a deep sense of loss and disconnection from home. Yet, the contemporary postmodern condition authorizes a genuine sense of longing for home even while dismantling hegemonic representation of homeland as stable. How this sense of mobile home(land) is created nevertheless becomes another issue. According to Mohammed Hirchi:

The word "home" can seem old-fashioned in some contexts. Some forms of cosmopolitanism embrace global rootlessness, valorizing citizens of the world with no fixed home, eschewing the local for the global. The postmodern emphasis on deconstruction, continual movement, and fluid identities can make home seem a stagnating, fuddy-duddy sort of place. And yet, one doesn't have to be nostalgic or hopelessly idealistic to see home as a legitimate longing, a genuine comfort, and something worth working hard to create. (305)

Mugo's longing for home can be said to be genuinely founded. It is at this point that the otherwise normative notion of home begins to yield itself to other postmodern meanings. They espouse the creation of new homes as response to the continual elusiveness of return

to an original homeland, real or imagined. Therefore, she "soaked""my mother's ears/ with my weeping" in a bid to reach out "for dialogue/ and home". This way, home could no longer be "found in exile" which is at the other end of the Atlantic. We are told that healing words eventually proceed from her mother whose perspectives interrogate her conservative sense of home. The first response calls to question the romanticisation of home when in reality the conditions of homeland are far from enviable. When such is the case, home, construed as an original place of attachment becomes an illusion. As has been discussed at the beginning of this essay, the entire collection for Mugo is an exercise in self-inscription and this validates the observation that "Throughout the centuries, exile has been an inspirational background for writers who exploit their personal experiences to touch on fundamental human issues" (Hirchi 305). In the subsequent lines, the persona's mother's rendition of home does not only caution on unnecessary romanticisation of original homeland. It also explores the conditions that instigate the construction and evolution of new spaces into other homes in place of original homelands. Of course, the knowledge that ever since her banishment in the 1980s Mugo has only returned to Kenya on occasional visits is an indication that the admonition to create other homes from home speaks to her exilic condition.

The mother's reply is instructive and deserves quoting in length in order to come to terms with some of the issues that are sometimes synonymous with conditions of original homelands:

For many who are home
have jail
for home
Thousands who are home
have streets
for home
Millions who are home
are crying
for home

The whole land
is crying:
for home

The whole land
is crying:
"The waters are bitter
what shall we drink?"

With such sundry forbidding conditions characterising home, any sense of nostalgia gives way to contemplations of alternative homes built away from the dangers associated with an original home. That such conditions can be wholly overwhelming is brought to the

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foreground in "the whole land/ is crying/for home" (80). The mother's response speaks more directly to Mugo's life experience when she further says:

*Daughter, do not
romanticize home
Do not, daughter
You who have*

*chosen the path
of people's struggles
must find the courage
to build new homes
to start new lives (81)*

That this speaks more directly to her is borne out by the persistence of state highhandedness for which Mugo was banished and stripped of her Kenyan citizenship in the first place. Knowing that many others like Ngugi suffered similar fate during Moi's tyrannical rule, we are able to come to terms with the import of the poem. It is as a critique of the limits of romanticism where homeland is concerned especially when it means incarceration and death for dissident voices. Mugo's exile poetry, like Iossif Ventura's thus demonstrates the externalisation of "well-hidden trauma that was engraved on [...her] unconscious" (Goldwyn 23). Against this backdrop, the autobiographical value of the poem is underscored by the contention that:

For the politically exiled, *going home* means more than taking a journey to the place where one was born. The ability to go, the decision to embark on such trip, and the experience of crossing borders to one's "native" land involves an "interrogation" of the makeup of the individual and the collective self; a definition and a redefinition of the meaning and the location of *home*; and a reexamination of one's current and former political commitments (Abdulhadi 89)

As simulation of the internal conflicts playing out in the mind of the poet, the conversations become a way of resolving issues around the right attitude about home. It speaks to Mugo's past and present commitments to the struggle for a better homeland and which has resulted in her exile. She firmly remains as persuaded about the idea of the "people's struggles". Where this is the case, the idea of home does not only become problematic; it also calls for the creation of another home from home in order to be guaranteed of safety. By taking to the advice of her mother in the telephone dialogue, the internal conflicts are resolved. This is clear in the metaphor of the sun shining "through/ the telephone line/as I looked beyond/ the day after/ my father/was buried (82). It is instructive to note that the idea of looking "beyond" transcends the sorrows of mourning in the wake of the burial. It speaks more importantly to the necessity of resolving to seek solace and satisfaction in building and nurturing a new home in diaspora. Original homeland, for that matter, is not safe because the resolve to keep on interrogating the status quo has not changed. It also brings to focus

the veracity of the assertion that being overwhelmed by nostalgia and the craving for return, we tend to forget that it is one thing for an exile to return, yet another thing to find fulfilment in that act of return (Porter 289). Finding fulfilment is therefore a function of what the current situation of homeland has to offer.

Conclusion

For Mugo, the uncertainty of what home may offer meant creating a new home far away from home as her life has shown, and seeing that since the 1980s she has remained in exile, settling in the United States. The distance from home has also offered her the privilege of commenting with a certain level of candour. It speaks not only to her personal condition, but also to the conditions of others both as people living at home and others living in exile like herself. Above all, her love for Africa as homeland and people of African descent and humanity in general in spite of the decision to remain in exile is unmistakable in this collection. It presents life as fraught with daunting challenges posed by agencies and institutions of power when misused. She nevertheless leaves readers with a ray of hope and optimism in the assurance that runs through all the poems in the collection that: forbidding regimes-- local and international-- can be brought to their knees for the triumphant celebration of justice after human rights interventions and the people's resilience have paid off.

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